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**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
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ASSESSMENT OF THE CAUSES AND STRATEGIES OF CONTROLLING SLUM DEVELOPMENT IN MARARABA, KARU LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *World's population has now shifted from predominantly rural to urban. As Majority of people now live in cities and towns and this shift reflects the astonishing trend towards urbanization that has occurred over the last several decades. This study seeks to assess the causes and strategies of controlling slum development, in Mararaba, Karu Local Government Area, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. A combination of primary and secondary sources was employed, including field observations, questionnaires, and interviews, utilizing a stratified sampling technique, the collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings indicate that the causes of slum include high rate of rural-urban migration, shortage of accommodation in well planned areas, cheap house rent in slum areas and relatively low cost of building structures in slum area. Slum can be controlled by government's dispossession of natives their slums potentials land, government control of sale and resale of land and enforcing compliance to building specifications by Town Planning Authority. Controlling slum can be improved by good utilities layout, drainages and sewage disposal systems. Since it will difficult to dispossess the natives and the landlords their property for proper development, the government should improve the social amenities in existing slum area through road network and construction of drainages. The government should compensate those whose properties will be affected.*

Keywords: Slum, Strategies, Causes, Control, Planning

INTRODUCTION

The world's population has now shifted from predominantly rural to urban (Davis, 2006). Majority of people now live in cities and towns and this shift reflects the astonishing trend towards urbanization that has occurred over the last several decades. In 1975, the urban population represented just over a third of the world's population (UN-HABITANT, 2002). In 1950, "there were 86 cities in the world with a population of more than one million; today there are 400, and by 2015 will be at least 550." (Davis, 2006). With this trend it is projected that in a short while, cities will house virtually all additional

population growth (UN-HABITANT, 2002) and this immense urbanization will be felt most strongly in developing countries. Between 1950 and 2000, the percentage of the population in developing countries living in cities and towns rose from 18 per cent to 40 per cent, and this percentage is expected to rise to 56 per cent by 2030 (Davis, 2006)

The growth of cities and towns is attributed to two main causes : (1 migration from rural areas, and 2 natural population growth. Among those who migrate to urban areas, the reasons underlying their migration vary. One of the primary reasons identified and discussed in the literature of

urbanization and migration are economic: simply put, individuals often come to urban areas in search of jobs and the opportunity to earn more income than they can earn in rural areas (Shandra et al, 2003)

The growth of slum has become a natural indicator of the process of the country's urbanization. It is estimated that at least 60 percent of the urban population lives in slums. It is also estimated by (UN-HABITAT 2002) that nearly 1 billion people live in slums in the cities of the world. That is one-sixth of humanity! Every single second, somewhere around the world, one person moves into a slum or squatter settlement. Most of these slums are in the cities / towns of the developing countries of the world. The annual urban growth rate in Sub-Saharan Africa is almost 5 percent, twice as high as in Latin America and Asia. It has also the world's largest proportion of urban residents living in slums, which today are a home to 72 percent of urban Africa's citizens representing a total of some 187 million people. With the adoption of the UN Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in 2000, the poor living conditions in unplanned urban settlement were placed on the global development agenda. UN statistics indicate that by 2020, more than 1.5 billion people will live in slums and informal settlements without significant intervention to improve access to water, sanitation, secure tenure and adequate housing.

The term "urbanization and urban poverty" describes the process of cities becoming more and more the places where the poor of the world can be found (Ogunyemi, 1998). These areas are thickly populated with low-income earners and are characterized by haphazardly erected structures of poor quality often lacking amenities with deteriorating conditions of living and lack of utilities layout around it.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A quantitative and qualitative research approach was adopted for this study. The survey of the study area was carried out to obtain firsthand information and for identifying the extent of the study area and also to determine and confirm the level of slum in the study area.

DATA COLLECTION METHODS

To achieve the aim of this study, two different sources of data were employed by the researcher. The sources of data employed by the researcher are as follows:

- i. = Primary source of data and
- ii = Secondary source of data.

PRIMARY SOURCE OF DATA

The primary sources of data collection are done through the administering of questionnaire, interview and field survey in respect of the study area.

PRIMARY DATA

QUESTIONNAIRE

According to Akeurezuilo (2004) a structured questionnaire would achieve greater uniformity and enable the researcher to obtain aggregate information in a uniform and standardized way. Such a procedure minimizes the element of "unevenness" in the response of the individual respondent as well as reduces "biases" on the part of the interviewers. However, it will be difficult to prepare a questionnaire that will cover every aspect of slums development in mararaba gurku area within the frame of time and other resources of this research. Nevertheless, it is believed that the questionnaires distributed will satisfy the objective of this study (see table 1 and 2 below).

PERSONAL INTERVIEW

In qualitative research, interviewing is one of the most important research tools for data collections. An interview is seen as a kind of social interaction between interviewing and interviewees. The interviewer faced varied challenges in interviewing. Thus, a possible first step in the initial design stage of interview was to address the

questions of what kind of data is required and how and from whom it was generated.

The author equally had an interview with Nasarawa Urban Development Board officials, Town Planning officials and ward heads of Karu Area. A total of ten (10) interviews were conducted during the field survey.

Table 1: Interview with the wards Heads, NUDB and Town planning officials

S/ N	Names of wards, NUDB and TPL official	Numbers of People Interview.
1	NUDB	2
2	Town Planning Official	1
3	Kabayi ward	1
4	Ochobo ward	1
5	Zamani ward	1
6	Deeper life Junction	1
7	Aso Road	1
8	Baba ward	1
9	Abacha Road	1

Source: Author Field Survey, 2022

Observation methods were used in this study. This method was used to ascertain the observable situation and also enabled the researcher to ascertain the interpretation of what was said during the interviews with the stakeholders as well as what I read from the official documents of Nasarawa State as regards to slums development in the state.

SECONDARY SOURCES OF DATA

These are data obtained through materials such as: text books, Journals, Newspapers, Magazines and

past dissertations related to this research.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The population of this study focus only in the residence of Karu area of Nasarawa State. The opinion survey of this population is sought because the study was centered on the impact of slums development on environment.

SAMPLING

Based on the nature of population to be sampled, a stratified random sample techniques

were adopted. This is because the researcher, the author has target on the resident of Karu area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. As such to ascertain the impact of slums development on environment in Mararaba Gurku area of Nasarawa State. This stratified random involves dividing the Karu into different zones known as street/ward. The high degree of selection involve, is meant to guarantee an even representation of all the strata in the sample as observed, stratified random sampling is very useful in ascertaining research situations, where the goals of generalizing on the population is not needed. Thus, the total of two hundred and fifty (250) questionnaires were randomly sampled among the population of about 256,800. They ward/street are; Baba ward, Abacha Road, Kabayi ward, Ochobo

ward, Zamani ward, Deeper Life Junction and Aso Road.

The Questionnaires were prepared and served to the residence that is, those that reside within the Mararaba Gurku area. The population of Karu Area of Nasarawa State is about 256,800, it has seven (7) ward and a total of two hundred and fifty (250) questionnaire for household for data collection. For this research purpose, the researcher uses stratified random sampling method for questionnaire administration, houses were selected randomly. In each building, household heads were met and interviewed or their spouse where the household head was absent. The table below gives summary of the study sampling framework.

Table 2: Questionnaires distributed base on wards.

S/N	Names Of Ward	No of Household	Numbers of questionnaires to be distribute
1	Baba ward	84	36
2	Abacha Road	70	36
3	Kabayi	80	36
4	Ochobo ward	60	35
5	Zamani ward	64	35
6	Deeper life Junction	64	36
7	Aso Road	65	36

Source: Field Survey, 2022

During the research, household selected and could not respond to the research questions due to certain reasons were immediately substituted. This ensured that the target two hundred and fifty (250) households were gotten. The knowledge of household's numbers and streets in Karu area were obtained from the 2006 population and housing census data.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

Percentages were the basic techniques of analysis used for result presentation. Other techniquessuch as tables were also employed amongst others.

Result was presented using percentage which was obtained through the use of the formula

$$\frac{X}{100n}$$

Where X= Variable
 n = Total Population Y= Resultant Percentage

STUDY AREA

Karu Town is the administrative Headquarters of Karu Local Government Area that share common boundaries with the Federal Capital Territory to the West, Kaduna State to the North and Keffi

Local Government Area to the East and Nasarawa Local Government Area to the South. Its location is marked approximately by latitudes 9° 00’ and 9° 15’N and longitudes 7° 45, and 8° 00’E(See figure 1). The study area is well served with inter-city road network. It is also one of the Major towns bordering the nation’s Federal Capital, Abuja.

Fig 1: The Study Area
 Source: Ministry of Lands and Survey, 2016

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CAUSES OF SLUMS DEVELOPMENT IN KARU

The causes of slums in Karu Local Government

Council (LGC), like in many other urban areas in developing countries, are multifaceted and can be attributed to a combination of social, economic, and environmental factors. The table below shows the causes of slum development in the study area

Table 3: Causes of Slum Development in the Study Area

Causes	Frequency of respondents	Percentage
(a) High rate of rural- Urban drift (migration)	62	31
(b) Shortage of accommodation in the decent areas of the city	59	29.5
(c) House rent is relatively low	31	15.
(d) Buildings are cheap to erect Here	13	6.5
(e) All of the above	35	17.5
Total	200	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

A large percentage of respondents (31 %) attribute emergence of slum to high rate of rural-urban drift. 29.5percent attribute it to shortage of accommodation in the decent area of the city. 15.5percent attribute slum to relatively low rent being for house in such areas. 6.5 percent attribute its cheap cost of building houses in such areas while 17.5 percent attribute slum to all these

factors.As house rent continues to rise, the poor individuals who cannot afford it look for alternatives cheap house found in slums. Soon new but cheap settlement develops in such places. Again, owners of land find it cheap to erect poorly designed structure which they offer at relatively cheap rent to those who are in dire need of accommodation.

Table 4: Strategies for Controlling Slums in Karu.

Strategy	Frequency of respondents	Percentage
(a) Natives should be prevented from selling land without approval from appropriate authority urban drift	60	30
(b) People should be prevented from building without authorized/plan approval	30	15
(c) All constructions in Authorized areas should beAccording to specifications	60	30
(d) Only the government shouldMap out areas of settlement	50	25
Total	200	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The results in table 4 shows the following strategies for slum control 60% said of natives should be controlled from selling land without approval from appropriate authority; 15 percent are of the view that people should be controlled from building without authorized / plan approval; all construction in authorized areas should be according to specification while 25 percent indicated that only the government should map out areas for settlement.

All these strategies are control measures that will bring the sale and development of plots of lands under government supervision. If the natives are

effectively checked in selling undeveloped plots of land to settlers and people are prevented from settling in unauthorized areas it means that only the government should authorize the sale and development of land. It lies on the government to specify building patterns to those it allocates land and only government should decide areas to be developed. This can be achieved through effective legislation by state Edict. These measures will control the indiscriminate selling of land by the natives which led to slum development in Mararaba and other slums in the Nasarawa State (See table 5)

Table 5: Strategies for controlling slums in Karu.

Others	Frequency of Respondents	Percentage
(a) Government should construct Roads and drainages in approve Areas before commencement of Any project	64	32
(b) Poor structure Should be prohibited	33	16.5
(c) Town planning authority Should specify building	43	21.5
(d) Re-sale of land should be authorized by appropriate authority	60	30
Total	200	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

From Table 5, 32 percent indicated that government should construct roads and drainages in approved areas before commencement of any project; 16.5 percent indicated that poor structures should be prohibited; 21.5 indicated that Town planning authority should specify building patterns; while 30 percent indicated that the re-sale of land should be authorized by appropriate authority. To ensure effective drainage in the areas, the government should first of all construct roads and drainage

system in the areas. Secondly, other social amenities should be provided before constructions begin. Preventing prefabricated structures will ensure that only model building is constructed according to specifications of Town planning Authority. Preventing re-sale of land or doing this only through the planning authority will ensure that nobody owns a piece of land in the area without government's knowledge and approval.

Table 6: Factors Militating Against Slum Control.

Factors	Frequency of Respondents	Percentage
(a) Resistance by	81	40.5
(b) Non-compliance by landlord	52	26
(c) Ineffective land laws	20	10
(d) Exorbitant cost of executing the plan	35	17.5
Total	200	100

Source: Authors Field Survey, 2022

From table 6, the major factors include residence by natives (41%), followed by non-compliance by landlord (26%). The least is ineffective land laws (10%). The natives of Mararaba and Masaka and other slum will not easily give up their land to the government to control its sale or re-sale. Even landlords do not comply with directives on how to build houses or provide sewage systems. The

resistance and non-compliance have been attributed to ineffective laws of the state in respect of land use. Moreover, huge cost is involved relocation of slum dwellers as it involves in allocation of new plots and low-cost housing development. Government cannot afford this at this stage.

Table 7: Ways of Making Slum Control Measures More Effective.

Ways	Frequency of Respondents	Percentage
(a) Enacting effective laws	79	39.5
(b) Using effective task force	48	24
(c) Empowering local leaders to check constructions.	73	36.5
Total	200	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

From Table 7, 39.5 percent indicated that enacting effective laws should be applied; 24 percent indicated that using effective task force be adopted while 36.5 percent indicated that empowering local leaders to check construction should also be adopted.

of sub-standard house, drainages and sewage disposal systems. Effective task force comprising law enforcement agents, town planning authority staff and land use. They should pull down illegal structure on sighting them. Besides, local leaders can use their men to ensure compliance with the land use laws.

Effective legislation on land use will prevent unauthorized settlements as well as construction

CONCLUSION

The assessment of the causes and strategies for controlling slum development in Mararaba, Karu Local Government Area, Nasarawa State, Nigeria, has shed light on several crucial aspects of urban development and housing in the region. Through an in-depth analysis of the factors contributing to slum development and the potential strategies for its control, this research has generated valuable insights for policymakers, urban planners, and community stakeholders.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The government of Nasarawa State should prioritize urban development policies that promote affordable housing, improved infrastructure, and effective urban planning. These policies should consider the unique challenges faced by Mararaba. Encourage collaboration between the public and private sectors to invest in affordable housing projects and infrastructure development.

REFERENCES

- Akeurezuilo, E. C. (2004). An examination of the urban housing problems in Nigeria: The case of Enugu Metropolis. *Environment and Behaviour*, 36(2), 275–300.
- Davis, M. (2006). *Planet of slums*. Verso.
- Ogunyemi, B. A. (1998). Urbanization and poverty: A Nigerian perspective. *African Urban Quarterly*, 13(2), 233–248.
- Shandra, J. M., Shandra, C. L., & London, B. (2003). World Bank structural adjustment, water, and sanitation: A cross-national analysis of child mortality in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Organization & Environment*, 16(4), 411–435.
- UN-HABITAT. (2002). *The challenge of slums: Global report on human settlements 2003*. United Nations Human Settlements Programme.